

Unsuitable by Design? Geospatial Evaluation of England's New Town Proposals

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Summary

This paper evaluates the environmental sustainability and climate resilience of the UK Government's proposed twelve new towns using high resolution datasets, spatial multi criteria analysis and participatory GIS. Findings show several sites face significant risks including flooding, overheating, water scarcity and ecological disruption, highlighting a misalignment between proposed locations and environmental constraints. Integrating participatory GIS with the NERC Digital Solutions Hub demonstrates how transparent, data rich tools enable stakeholders to explore scenarios and identify more suitable alternatives. The study proposes a national framework that embeds environmental intelligence, digital infrastructures and public participation into early-stage planning to ensure sustainable, climate resilient development.

KEYWORDS:

Environmental sustainability assessment; Climate-risk modelling, PPGIS, new town planning and resilience, www.digital-solutions.uk

1. Introduction

The UK Government's proposal to develop twelve new towns represents a major strategic intervention in national spatial planning at a time when climate change, ecological decline and regional inequalities are placing increasing pressure on existing settlement structures. Although framed around sustainability and resilience, early assessments suggest that several proposed locations may be environmentally unsuitable. This paper evaluates the environmental sustainability and climate resilience of the proposed sites, as shown in Figure 1, using high resolution environmental datasets, spatial multicriteria analysis and participatory GIS (PPGIS) methodologies. It also demonstrates the potential of the NERC funded Digital Solutions Hub (DSH) as a national digital infrastructure enabling transparent, data rich and participatory evaluation of development proposals.

2. Environmental Data and Climate Risk Assessment

Drawing on datasets available via the NERC DSH, including UKCP18 climate projections, hydrological models, fluvial and surface water flood risk maps, soils and land carbon inventories, biodiversity indicators, landcover transitions and ecosystem service layers, the analysis evaluates each of the twelve new town locations against key sustainability criteria. Several sites lie within medium to high-risk flood zones, with some expected to experience increased flood hazard frequency under anticipated climate change pathways (Sayers et al., 2020; IPCC, 2022). Rising summer temperatures and longer dry periods projected under high emissions scenarios raise concerns about water availability, overheating and future energy demand.

Ecological datasets show that multiple sites overlap with priority habitats, environmentally sensitive landscapes or ecological network corridors central to national nature recovery ambitions (Natural

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England, 2023). Without substantial mitigation, development in these areas risks long-term ecological fragmentation. These findings reflect longstanding concerns within planning literature about tensions between growth led spatial strategies and the environmental constraints shaping long-term land use viability (Campbell, 1996; Godschalk et al, 2013).

Figure 1 The 12 proposed new town locations (inset) and 5 sites in SE England.

3. Sustainability, New Settlements and Planning Theory

The history of new town development in the UK demonstrates that successful planning requires deep integration of environmental evidence, spatial design principles and community needs (Jenks & Dempsey, 2005; Healey, 2010). With accelerating climate impacts, aligning new development locations with long-term climate projections is essential to minimising vulnerability and avoiding maladaptive settlement patterns (Adger, 2006).

Yet the evidence presented here (see Figure 2) shows a misalignment between several proposed locations and the environmental constraints highlighted by available datasets. This indicates a broader structural issue: the underuse of environmental data infrastructures and climate risk modelling in national planning decisions (Goodchild, 2007; Batty, 2013). Without systematic integration of environmental intelligence at early planning stages, new settlements risk undermining their stated sustainability objectives.

Figure 2 Environmental risks at 12 locations analysed using the DSH ‘Where to Build App’ (Note – legend from Figure 1 applies here too.)

4. Participatory GIS and Democratic Spatial Decision Making

Beyond technical assessments, the legitimacy of spatial planning depends on transparency, inclusivity

and meaningful public engagement. Over two decades of research in (Public) Participatory GIS has shown how web-based mapping tools allow communities and stakeholders to engage with spatial information, explore development scenarios and contribute local knowledge to planning processes. Early PPGIS work (Kingston et al, 2000) demonstrated how interactive online platforms support scenario exploration, deliberation and public understanding of spatial trade-offs by enabling users to visualise alternative outcomes and express preferences within shared geographic interfaces.

Subsequent studies emphasise how online participatory mapping can broaden access to spatial information, reduce barriers to engagement and enhance the deliberative quality of local policy processes. In climate adaptation contexts, PPGIS tools have illuminated community level understandings of environmental risk and contributed to coproduced adaptation strategies. For example, participatory flood risk mapping has shown how community insights can complement modelling to improve the credibility and acceptance of adaptation options (White, Kingston & Barker, 2010). Applications in local serviced delivery contexts similarly demonstrate how residents' experiential knowledge can shape more responsive and context specific policy responses (Viitanen & Kingston, 2009).

This body of work highlights the capacity of PPGIS to mediate between expert environmental evidence and public perspectives, strengthening transparency and generating spatial decisions that are both analytically robust and socially legitimate (Elwood, Goodchild & Sui, 2012; McCall & Dunn, 2012).

5. Integrating PPGIS with the NERC Digital Solutions Hub

A key contribution of this study is demonstrating how participatory spatial approaches can be scaled nationally through integration with the DSH. The DSH provides federated environmental datasets, cloud-based analytics, standardised metadata, open APIs and reproducible geoprocessing workflows. When linked with PPGIS interfaces, these capabilities enable stakeholders, including planners, local authorities, environmental NGOs, developers and residents to access and interpret environmental evidence directly.

The conceptual architecture links PPGIS tools and stakeholder inputs at the front end with the analytical functions of the DSH. Participants can interactively explore environmental layers, for example, overlaying proposed development footprints on flood risk surfaces, assessing climate projections for specific sites, evaluating ecological connectivity impacts or comparing alternative spatial configurations. Such integration reduces technical and institutional barriers traditionally associated with spatial data access, aligning with broader arguments for open environmental governance, digital democracy and citizen participation in environmental decision making (Janssen et al., 2012; Kitchin, 2014).

6. Participatory Assessment of the New Town Proposals

To test the DSH framework, a participatory evaluation was conducted with representatives from local government, planning consultancies, environmental organisations (e.g. Defra, EA, Met Office) and community groups who attended DSH workshops held in November 2025. Participants used interactive mapping tools linked to DSH NERC and other openly available environmental datasets to undertake site-specific evaluations based on flood exposure, climate risk projections, ecological sensitivity and long-term sustainability indicators. Four key insights emerged:

- **Environmental vulnerability is underestimated.** Participants identified environmental risks, especially flood exposure, heat-stress vulnerability and ecological fragmentation, that were not sufficiently recognised in official planning documents.
- **More environmentally suitable locations exist.** With access to environmental datasets and scenario testing tools, stakeholders identified alternative locations with greater long-term climate resilience and fewer ecological conflicts.
- **Transparency improves trust and decision quality.** Shared access to environmental

evidence reduced scepticism about planning assumptions and encouraged more constructive dialogue.

- **Digital infrastructures narrow participation gaps.** The DSH workflow enabled nonspecialists to engage directly with complex climate and environmental data, supporting more inclusive and climate justice oriented planning processes (Agyeman, 2013).

7. Discussion: A Framework for Evidence Driven and Participatory Planning

These findings reinforce the need for planning systems that integrate environmental intelligence, participatory governance and digital infrastructure. Sustainable development cannot be achieved solely through top-down site selection or narrow economic criteria; it demands a synthesis of scientific analysis, community engagement and long-term ecological stewardship (Campbell, 1996; Healey, 2010).

By linking participatory GIS methodologies with the computational capacities of the DSH, this study advances a model for transparent, evidence driven and collaborative spatial decision making. This model enhances analytical capacity while enabling diverse stakeholders to shape development trajectories in ways that reflect environmental constraints and social aspirations.

Most sustainable	Moderately sustainable	Less sustainable
Sites in urban locations with lower flood risk	Located close to larger urban areas but flood risk relatively high	Good quality agricultural land, flood risk and protected areas
Site 6 – Victoria North, Manchester	Site 11 – Thamesmead Riverside	Site 1 – Adlington
Site 5 - Leeds South Bank but with some flood risk	Site 3 – Chase Park / Crews Hill	Site 4 – Heyford Park
Site 2 – Brabazon	Site 10 – Tempsford	Site 8 – Milton Keynes Renewal
Site 9 – Plymouth		Site 7 – Marlcombe
		Site 12 – Worcestershire Parkway

Table 1 summary of most and least sustainable sites

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

The long-term success of the UK Government’s new towns programme depends on embedding environmental and climate risk evidence, participatory methods and digital infrastructures into early stage planning. This paper recommends that:

- Environmental datasets and climate risk projections be integrated from the outset using platforms such as the DSH.
- Participatory GIS methodologies be embedded in statutory consultation processes, enabling public interrogation of spatial evidence.
- New settlement development aligns with climate adaptation and nature recovery strategies, avoiding maladaptive patterns.
- Digital literacy and participatory mapping skills be strengthened nationally, ensuring equitable access to environmental data.
- Open data and federated analytical infrastructures be adopted to support transparent, accountable planning.

By combining environmental modelling, climate risk intelligence and participatory GIS, this study provides a robust framework for evaluating and improving the sustainability of major development proposals. As climate change intensifies, spatial decisions must be transparent, collaborative and attuned to long-term environmental realities. The integrated PGIS DSH architecture offers a scalable model for achieving these outcomes.

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You can find out user testing environment here <https://nerc-digital-solutions-hub.github.io/dsh-testing/> and over time we will publish our source code after external assessment from the Software Sustainability Institute here <https://github.com/NERC-Digital-Solutions-Hub>

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